

Retirement and Redesign and of pages; introduction to group workspace

Discussion document

Background

The IPCC DDC has range of pages discussing complex issues, and in some cases the content is dated and possibly misleading (see examples below). The problem is made worse by the ambiguity around the status of web pages: are they intended to be kept up to date or should they be considered as a record of the views held at some time in the past?

Updating pages which contain scientific content requires careful review in order to ensure that any changes accurately reflect a consensus across the IPCC. It can often be the case that issues are under discussion for years, in which case there is no current consensus to refer to.

General principles

We propose the following general principles:

- (1) Discussion of science issues should be in a fact sheets --- possibly linked to a specific IPCC Assessment Round or Rounds.
- (2) Links to IPCC DDC data resources should be via catalogue records which contain the appropriate technical and publishing information (e.g. authors, date of publication).

Specific Examples

CO2 page (http://www.ipcc-data.org/observ/ddc_co2.html)

This is a popular page, consistently attracting high numbers of viewers, but the information is primarily relevant to AR4.

Environmental Data and Scenarios

(http://www.ipcc-data.org/observ/ddc_envdata.html)

This page contains some links to old scenario data, and general comments on some atmospheric constituents (e.g. ozone, sulphur dioxide),

What is a GCM

(http://www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/pages/gcm_guide.html)

Extremely old text .. fact sheet in preparation.

Weather generators

(http://www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/pages/weather_generators.html)

The page makes references to various articles, the most recent of which is “Mearns et al. (2001)”, but does not provide the full references. The weather generator is just one example of downscaling techniques, and it is not clear why it has a page here.

Scenario selection

(http://www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/pages/scen_selection.html)

This is a short text, which may have contributed to an early scenario development process. It was not really relevant to the AR5 process.

Options

(1) Copy content into a legacy factsheet ... without updating

In this case, the content will be maintained with clear dating, so that people can refer to it in order to understand what was done at the time, but will be aware of its limitations.

(2) Adapt content to reflect current understanding .. in a new fact sheet.

The modified content will, of course, need review.

(3) Both 1 and 2.

In some cases we may wish to both preserve information about the approaches used in the past and develop a new fact sheet.

CEDA Catalogue Pages

The screenshot shows the CEDA Catalogue interface. At the top, there is a header for the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, including contact information and social media links. Below the header is a search bar with a dropdown menu, an input field for search terms, and a 'GO!' button. The main content area features a navigation menu with 'Catalogue Home', 'Catalogue Intro', 'Advanced Search', and 'Admin login'. The central focus is a dataset entry for 'WCRP CMIP5: Canadian Centre for Climate Modelling and Analysis (CCCma) CanAM4 model output collection'. This entry includes a 'Dataset Collection' section with publication details: 'Publication State: Published', 'Publication Date: 2017-03-17', and 'DOI Publication Date: No DOI'. Below this is an 'Abstract' section with a 'COMMENTS' button. The 'Abstract' text reads: 'WCRP CMIP5: Canadian Centre for Climate Modelling and Analysis (CCCma) CanAM4 model output collection.' It also includes a 'Citable as:' section with citation information and a 'Keywords:' section listing 'CMIP5, WCRP, climate change, CCCma, CanAM4'. To the right of the abstract is a 'Temporal Range' section showing dates from '1950-01-16T12:00:00' to '2010-01-01T00:00:00', and a 'Geographic Extent' section with a world map showing the data's spatial coverage.

Example page at <http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/de2e30c90eb7449c8cbcf9b45c7a1192>

CEDA catalogue pages provide a structured description of data archived at CEDA. Links to descriptions of models and institutions are provided.

Introducing the IPCC DDC Data Access Server

An ongoing concern for providing global access to data resources has been the limited IT functionality and bandwidth available to certain members of the community (particularly in developing nations). This has provided a fundamental barrier to certain groups being able to contribute to the science and application of climate change information. In response to this issue an interactive login service will be deployed on the JASMIN data-processing platform at STFC that allows direct SSH (i.e. terminal) login for registered users. The majority of these users are expected to be IPCC Authors.

Figure 1 illustrates how this service will work. Within the JASMIN platform CEDA will provide an interactive server for data processing. This will be able to read from the major CEDA archives: including over 1Pbyte of existing climate data holdings (such as CMIP5 and CORDEX). Additionally, a 20Tbyte workspace will be made available for writing, storing and sharing outputs generated by the IPCC Authors working on the interactive server. Login to

JASMIN will happen directly from the end user's local computer (anywhere in the world) via a gateway server. Each user will have access to an SSH terminal in order to organise and run their own data analysis.

Figure 1: Overview of the interactive login server and connectivity to end users.

A JASMIN virtual server (*ddc-sci1.ceda.ac.uk*) will be set up in the JASMIN environment with the following characteristics:

- 16Gbytes of RAM
- 16 CPUs (processors)
- Software environment: "JASMIN Analysis Platform" including common tools such as netCDF4 libraries, Climate Data Operators, NetCDF Operators, cpython, iris, matplotlib etc. Details of all packages are visible at: https://github.com/cedadev/jasmin_scivm/wiki/packages
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- 20 Tbytes of disk space for general use (group work space);
- 20 Tbytes of tape for backup;
- /badc/ archives mounted read-only (but some data cannot be read directly because of access controls: it may be necessary to copy data across to the 20Tb group work space for processing. There is a very fast internal network, so this transfer will be extremely fast.

It is important to note that logins from around the world will be required from known institutions (with fixed IP addresses) as connections from dynamic IP hosts are not permitted. Typically this means that users will need to login from their work institutions.

Proposals:

- (1) First year of use should be to evaluate the usefulness.
- (2) TSUs and TGICA should determine who gets access to the machine, and best usage of the disk spec (which is likely to fill up quickly);